

The Influence of SAMs on the Performance and Stability of Perovskite Solar Cells

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Abstract

Self-assembled monolayers (SAMs) are promising candidates to replace conventional hole-transport layers (HTLs) in perovskite solar cells (PSCs). However, the fundamental mechanisms by which SAMs influence perovskite crystal growth and device stability remain insufficiently understood. In this work, we investigate two SAMs, Me-4PACz and F-4PACz, that differ in their functional groups. Although perovskite films exhibit improved wetting on F-4PACz, the resulting devices show a reduced fill factor (FF).

To elucidate the origin of this behaviour, we examine the perovskite crystal structure on both SAMs using Kelvin probe force microscopy (KPFM), atomic force microscopy (AFM), X-ray diffraction (XRD), grazing-incidence wide-angle X-ray scattering (GIWAXS), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) and photoluminescence (PL) mapping. Furthermore, we assess charge-transport properties across the two SAMs and their corresponding device stacks using ultraviolet photoelectron spectroscopy (UPS), transient surface photovoltage (trSPV) and time-resolved photoluminescence (trPL).

This study provides deeper insight into how SAMs govern interfacial energetics, perovskite growth and ultimately the performance and stability of PSCs.

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